

A Conceptual Study on Establishing Social Enterprise Company with Institutional Theory Approach

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ABSTRACT

This conceptual paper discussed on the importance of establishing Social Enterprise Companies with a Theoretical approach. Social Enterprises are becoming the new vehicle of business for many entrepreneurs who are combating to solve a social issues or problems. It is important for this enterprise to establish their organisation by comprehending with relevant framework and theories. Therefore, this paper was prepared for social enterprises to understand how an institutional theory might be applicable for their social venture. The study reviews literatures and relevant social enterprise framework and three factors related to Institutional Theory. Lastly, recommendations for social entrepreneur on how a theory can help to navigate their social enterprises were provided to allow them position with the Covid-19 pandemic that has shaken the world. In addition recommendations are provided to United Nations (UN) to have a study on the true numbers of social enterprises that are available to support the social needs and problems collectively as one world. Moreover, recommendations for future researcher are included.

Keywords: Institutional Theory, Social Enterprise, Social Entrepreneurship, Covid - 19

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1.0 Introduction

The world we are living in is no longer same. We are living in an environment that is constantly changing and the Covid – 19 Pandemic also known as coronavirus pandemic has pushed organization to revisit how it is operating. This includes social enterprise companies which are established to solve social issue or problems. It is important that social enterprises or social entrepreneurs to have an understanding on pre-establish frameworks and theories that can be incorporated during their setup. Hence, this paper has focused on how social enterprises can apply institutional theory as a guide during their formation. The study have reviewed various literatures regards to social enterprise and institutional theory by hoping that current and future social enterprises will benefit with the findings and discussion.

1.1 Background Study

Social enterprises are becoming a new vehicle for social entrepreneurs to solve social issues or problems. Abbatiello et al.,(2018) stated that there is a seismic change is happening with various organization that are no longer measuring the success of its company performance based on financial performance only and have begun to focus on the impact on society in a larger scale. In addition, it is found as the new social capital approach which combines revenue growth and profits that can support its stakeholders by serving with a purpose.

According to Leadbeater (2006), social entrepreneurs or enterprises are prepared to address problems in an innovative approach by providing new solutions. Usually social entrepreneurs are willing to transfer the new approaches that they discovered to public sectors if the problems can be mitigated or resolved. Moreover, social entrepreneur's works for creating assets for communities by applying social capital theory that asserts on partnership and alliances with shared values and trust. Zandi et al., (2019) pointed out that social enterprise approach are usually develop as a pilot project and then scaled with a purpose of tackling the social issues.

2.0 Review of Literature

There are various models and framework can be applied towards establishing a social enterprise. This paper points out few for the readers and social entrepreneurs to consider before establishing the company. It has to be noted that there is no data to state the real number of social enterprises established in the world. However, there are reports pointed out based on Europe, The United States, United Kingdom, Asia countries which included Malaysia Government who is actively providing finding ways to improve its services with social enterprise approach (Council, 2018).

2.1 Social Enterprise Type and Models

It is very important to select the suitable model for your social enterprise in this Covid – 19 Pandemic. According to Sivalingam & Mansori (2020), the pandemic have caused approximately 3.5 Trillion US Dollars to be wipe out that have caused significant impact to the world economy. Unemployment rate is rising high and multinational companies (MNC) are force to shut down as it can no longer survive. Banks are trying to rollout with stimulus packages hoping the economic will revive.

Hence, for the new comers to the social enterprise platform need to clearly understand that there is an opportunity to solve various social problems or it can also turn out to be a struggle. Force (2017) stated that there are nine (9) business models that can be used for social enterprises. Table 1 elaborates further.

Model	Model Type	Description
1	The Entrepreneur Support Model	This model of social enterprise (SE) sells business support services directly to the entrepreneurs in its target population. In other words, this type of SE helps entrepreneurs get their businesses off the ground. Support can come in the form of consulting services, training, microfinancing or technical support. Organizations that belong to this category may include economic development organizations, business development service organizations and microfinancers.
2	The Market Intermediary Model	This type of SE generally helps their clients by marketing or selling their clients' products or services for them. For example, an organization that helps struggling small farmers by marketing and to sell their crops for them would belong to this category.
3	The Employment Model	This type of SE provides their clients with job opportunities and job training. Revenue generated by those jobs pays for the SEs expenses and flows back into the services provided for those in need. Many youth and disabilities organizations adopt this model.
4	The Fee-for-Service Model	The fee-for-service model is one of the most commonly adopted SE business models. The SE charges the customer directly for the socially beneficial services it provides. Many hospitals, schools, museums and membership organizations use the fee-for-service model to a greater or less degree.
5	The Low Income Client Model	SEs in this category generally offer social services directly (as in the fee-for-service model) while focusing on low-income clients. Hospitals and healthcare programs that offer their healthcare services to low-income patients often adopt this model.
6	The Cooperative Model	This is one of the most widely recognized categories of SE. The cooperative is generally a fee-based membership organization that provides member services to a group that shares a common need or goal. The cooperative is owned and operated by its members, who both run the cooperative and receive the benefits of its success. Two of the most well-known types of cooperative include credit unions and employee-owned businesses ("co-ops").
7	The Market Linkage Model	SEs that serve as brokers for their clients often adopt this model. These SEs focus on building relationships and otherwise connecting their clients with markets for their clients' products and services. However, unlike SEs adopting the market <i>intermediary</i> model, these SEs generally do not market or sell their clients' products and services for them. Many trade associations adopt the market linkage model.
8	The Service Subsidization Model	This type of SE funds social programs by selling products or services in the marketplace. Service subsidization is one of the most common SE models, as almost any SE can adopt it. In contrast to organizational support SEs (see below), service subsidization SEs integrate their internal business with external social programs. For example, a law firm may use the revenue generated from the firm's regular law practice to fund a social program that provides free law services to those in need. The firm may run the program out of their own offices and may provide the free law services themselves.
9	The Organizational Support Model	This type of SE, like a service subsidization organization, sells products or services to fund social programs. However, the social programs they fund are part of a separate, parent organization. In other words, an organizational support SE raises funds for a parent non-profit that, in turn, runs the social programs the SE wishes to support.

Table 1 : 9 Business Model for Social Enterprise: Source : Adam G Force (2017)

Force (2017) further stated that there is always new models can be developed and will emerge beside the nine widely used models. This view was actually addressed by Danielle (2018) who claimed that there is ten(10) ways to have a creative approaches in designing a social enterprise business model that is focus on affordability in a sustainable way. Table 2 elaborates further.

RETHINK YOUR OFFER	CROSS SUBSIDIZE YOUR OFFERS	ADJUST YOUR COST MODEL	CROSS-SUBSIDIZE CUSTOMER SEGMENTS	GENERATE VALUE FOR A THIRD PARTY
OFFER FLEXIBLE REPAYMENT	PROVIDE A PAY-AS-YOU-GO OPTION	PROVIDE FINANCING	MOVE ALONG THE VALUE CHAIN	ADJUST YOUR SCALING STRATEGY

Table 2 : 10 Ways to address Affordability Source: Danielle Sutton (2018)

As pointed out earlier, it is important for social entrepreneurs or social enterprises to take into account the Covid-19 Pandemic and how it can adapt new changes to be relevant, sustainable and focus on the social mission. Therefore, the institutional theory can support to further design the best strategies that can be applied.

2.2 Institutional Theory

By reviewing the literatures by Scott (2004), he points out that Institutional Theory was first developed by Meyer & Rowan in 1977 and was further developed along the years with rich social sciences. It provides non – economic descriptions of behaviours and approaches by creating guidelines related to production, exchange and delivery. Thilo (2019) claims that institutional theory approach can be used on how organizations and individuals operates within the organisation and are interrelated at all times if it welcome changes to happen. In addition, Agrawal & Hockerts (2013) stated that institutional theory involves organisations, individuals and institution such as government, the market, culture and religion which studies the dynamic between the factors and they have elaborate on their study by presenting four cases of social entrepreneurship. It was interesting to review literatures from Jeferry (2012) which pointed out that institutional theory relates to change agent.

If anyone wants to make significant changes in their organisation or institution, he advises to take your group, team, department or your entire company in an entirely new significant direction rather than just following the crowd will not be a successful strategy. At this stage, the researcher recalls Steve Jobs, Founder of Apple. Inc, in how Steve manages to take bold steps by revolutionizing the telecommunication industry and entire mobile phones that we use today. This is very aligned to Jeferry (2012) views where he emphasized that to become an “Institutional Entrepreneur” he/she needs to be courageous to take the risk of developing or trying new methods that have not been field tested by other companies. This is when you will tend to build new strategies for your institution or company that will take you to a position when other might end up following your model and strategy. As for this paper, we can refer it to existing social enterprises or future social entrepreneurs should be brave to test out their ideas. Bruton et al.,(2010) study stated that institutional theory has been a popular theory mainly relate to entrepreneurial research and application. There is a need to establish more literatures on institutional theory which is gap. The review of the articles from Bruton et al.,(2010) clearly demonstrates that the institutional theory has become popular however, the application of the theory was otherwise.

2.2 Conceptual Institutional Theory and Social Entrepreneurship Framework

Bruton et al.,(2010) pointed out that there is there factors are related to institutional theory

- i* Institutional setting
- ii* legitimacy
- iii* Institutional entrepreneurship

While, Force (2017) stated there are 9 Model related to Social Entrepreneurship. Therefore, both this concepts have been integrated for future studies in this study by the authors.

3.0 Conclusion

The Covid – 19 Pandemic has surely caused many organizations globally to suffer and there is more sign the global economy will take time to bounce back hoping if there is non-other global issues. We have to agree that the world needs responsible organisation to be emerging and one of the best ways to have is by encouraging and developing more social entrepreneurs. Social enterprises should now begin to focus on more serious issues and problems to bring back a balance in the world by working with various governments collectively. This paper pointed out it is vital for the social entrepreneurs to understand the models that they can choose before starting up their venture and more importantly what problems are they planning to solve or mitigate. Furthermore, the paper also has given an introduction on how social enterprises can apply institutional theory as a guide during their formation. After reviewing the literatures and recommends, it can be concluded that the institutional theory is open to be transformed with the social enterprise models if the entrepreneurs or scholars is able to create applicable framework. *The Conceptual Institutional Theory and Social Entrepreneurship Framework* in this paper is recommended as a foundation for other researcher to dive in deeper which will allow social entrepreneurs bring solution to the pandemic have caused Trillion US Dollars to be wipe-out from the global market which could have used for building a better live for all.

4.0 Recommendation

Recommendation 1: To United Nations (UN)

There is no confirmation of how many social enterprises are existed in this world. Therefore, it is recommended that United Nations (UN) should take the lead to engage with its 193 member countries to identify social enterprises and social entrepreneurs who can be part of the global solution or national problems. The aim of United Nation can be achieved if there is a global eco-system developed for social entrepreneurs who are aligned with UN to maintain international peace, security, developing friendly relationship among nations, achieve international cooperation's. A trade and Global Database platform can be established for social entrepreneurs by registering them from major cities to remote villages. This will provide a platform for new social entrepreneurs to come forwards and maybe solve problems and issues collectively with governments and non-profit entity. In addition, inviting all level of social entrepreneurs and not only “famous” in a Think Tank group can be started. There is a need of “Global Social Entrepreneurs” and Social Entrepreneurs Development Grant should be available. This can create jobs and also solving problems.

Recommendation 2: To Future Researchers

There is a gap to *Institutional Theory* with *Social Entrepreneurs* and future studies should be carried out to provide recommendation on to how apply theories for new social entrepreneurs. There is no one way to start a study and it should be with a purpose stated (Hizam et al.,(2020)

Recommendation 3: To Social Entrepreneurs

Being and choosing to be a Social Entrepreneur is not to become famous and clouded with fame and Awards. It is a moral responsibility that Social Entrepreneur should understand when setting up their ventures. The problem that they are embarking to solve should be the main purpose why they have chosen to become social entrepreneurs. Therefore, it is recommended that Social Entrepreneur to clearly define why they have choose to become a Social Entrepreneur or establishing a Social Enterprise in the first place. Then they should also understand some theories that they can apply for their ventures and also can consider the Institutional Theory to begin with.

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